

Evaluation of the Role of Vitamin D on Pre-Eclampsia and its Correlates in Pregnancy: An Institution Based Observational Study**Rajanya Kar¹, SK. Washim Ali², Rishita Bose³, Prithwish Bandyopadhyay⁴, Saikat De⁵, Shyamapada Pati⁶**¹Senior Resident, College of Medicine & Sagore Dutta Medical College and Hospital²Senior Resident, Malda Medical College and Hospital³Senior Resident, IPGMER & SSKM Hospital⁴Senior Resident, Department of Community Medicine, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital⁵Demonstrator, Department of Community Medicine, Murshidabad Medical College and Hospital⁶Professor & HOD (Ex.), Calcutta National Medical College and Hospital

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Abstract:**Background:** Pre-eclampsia (PE), characterized by hypertension and proteinuria, poses significant risks to maternal health, including eclampsia and mortality. Vitamin D, essential for immune modulation and vascular health, showed potential in reducing the risk of pre-eclampsia and showed to potentially prevent hypertensive complications during pregnancy. This study aims to evaluate the role of vitamin D in preventing pre-eclampsia and eclampsia, along with finding out its correlates and associated maternal and perinatal outcomes.**Methodology:** This study was conducted in the department of obstetrics and gynaecology at Calcutta National Medical College and Hospital, Kolkata, over one and a half years among 111 ante-partum women admitted through the obstetric emergency or referred to the hospital, fulfilling inclusion & exclusion criteria. Ethical clearance and informed consent were sought. Data were collected by using a predesigned pretested semi-structured questionnaire following clinical examination and biochemical tests. Data were analyzed using SPSS, summarizing categorical variables as counts and percentages. Inferential statistics measured by Chi-square test. P-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.**Result:** Pre-eclampsia and eclampsia were observed in 15.3% and 6.3% of women respectively. About 24.5% of mothers who had developed pre-eclampsia had suboptimal levels of Vitamin D. Most pre-eclamptic mothers delivered by caesarean section (47.1%), with one-fourth of their babies being low-birth weight and 41.7% required SNCU admission.**Conclusion:** The potential link between suboptimal vitamin D levels and pre-eclampsia emphasized the importance of antenatal supplementation and further research to establish standard guidelines to prevent pre-eclampsia.**Keywords:** Pre-eclampsia, Eclampsia, Vitamin D deficiency, Low birth weight.

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Introduction

Hypertensive disorders in pregnancy, including gestational hypertension, pre-eclampsia (PE), and eclampsia, significantly contribute to maternal mortality (5-10%) and affect 1 in 12 to 17 pregnancies [1, 2]. Pre-eclampsia is triggered by impaired placentation and maternal systemic response, leading to severe complications like eclampsia, disseminated intravascular coagulation, and HELLP syndrome [1].

Vitamin D, a potent immunomodulator, promotes a Th2 response essential for normal pregnancy, countering the Th1 response associated with preterm labour and increased in pre-eclampsia [3]. Vitamin D shifts the balance to Th2 and stimulates suppressor T regulatory cells, preventing immune

intolerance during placentation. Deficiency in Vitamin D may lead to endothelial dysfunction, contributing to pre-eclampsia. Vitamin D, specifically 1, 25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃, regulates angiogenesis via VEGF gene transcription, associated with proteinuria and endothelial function [4]. Calcitriol, a form of Vitamin D, improves vascular health by preventing cholesterol uptake, reducing muscle proliferation, enhancing vascular compliance, and regulating blood pressure through calcium homeostasis and renin suppression, while modulating adipokines to promote endothelial and vascular health [5, 6, 7].

Maternal vitamin D deficiency, due to inadequate sunlight and insufficient intake despite regular use

of prenatal vitamins containing 400 IU of vitamin D3, is a significant public health issue during pregnancy [8]. Several hypotheses suggest hypovitaminosis D is linked to pre-eclampsia via various biological processes. In this context, the present study was conducted to evaluate the role of vitamin D in pre-eclampsia, as well as to find out its correlates and associated maternal and perinatal outcomes.

Materials & Methods: This institution based descriptive, observational study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology of Calcutta National Medical college and Hospital, Kolkata for a period of one and half year from February 2021 to July 2022. Hundred and eleven (111) antepartum women with gestational age between 34-40 weeks either in labour or admitted for obstetric complication and singleton pregnancies were investigated and evaluated as per objective. Mothers with medical conditions such as diabetes mellitus, thyroid disorders, chronic hypertension, acute fatty liver of pregnancy, cardiac disorders, severe anaemia, pre-existing chronic liver and renal diseases, haemolytic anaemia, bleeding disorders, carrying an IUD fetus, history of recurrent miscarriage, those on medication inhibiting vitamin D absorption, or unwilling to participate were excluded from the study.

Sampling Size and Sampling Technique: Sample size was calculated by considering a prevalence of 15% of pre-eclampsia from previous study [9], 5% of absolute precision and 10% non-response rate. The estimated sample size was 111. The study subjects were selected by purposive sampling technique.

Study Tool and Data Collection: Data were collected by interviewing the study participants using a predesigned pretested semi structured questionnaire after taking informed consent. Information regarding sociodemographic variables (like age, residence, educational status, socioeconomic status, booked/unbooked cases), a detailed history on gestational age (calculated according to LMP, sonographic examination before 20weeks if LMP not remembered),

present obstetric history (mode of delivery, birth weight of baby, SNCU admission, APGAR score) were obtained. Clinical examination including general (Height, weight, BMI, BP measurement), systemic and obstetric examination was done. Laboratory investigation like Hematological test (Hb%, platelet count, coagulation profile), Hepatic function test (serum bilirubin, AST, ALT, Alkaline phosphate), Kidney function test (blood urea, 24 hours urinary protein) Vitamin D level estimation by Sandwich ELISA method) was performed. Detailed history and ANC records were checked for intake of calcium and Vitamin D tablets as provided by the institution/ doctor she was seeking ANC care from. Birth weight of newborn was classified according to WHO criteria, pre-eclampsia and eclampsia was diagnosed according to criteria by ACOG, anemia was classified according to WHO criteria (Hb <11g%) and low platelet count(<1 lakh) as well as abnormal liver function tests was defined by ACOG criteria. Vitamin D value ≥ 25 ng/ml was considered optimal, while < 25 ng/ml was considered suboptimal.

Data Analysis: Data were entered into a Microsoft excel spreadsheet and then analyzed by SPSS (version 27.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Categorical variables were summarized as counts and percentages. Inferential statistics measured by using Chi square test. Odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence interval (CI) were also calculated. P value <0.05 was considered as significant.

Ethical Clearance: Ethical clearance was taken from institutional ethics committee vide EC-CNMC/2021/100(4) dated 27.01.2021. Permission was taken from the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, CNMCH.

Result and Analysis:

Background Characteristics: The majority of mothers (75.7%) were aged 20 or older, with a mean age of 21.54 ± 2.837 years. Nearly half of the mothers (48.7%) had education up to lower secondary level, and most belonged to the lower middle class (40.5%) [Table-1].

Table 1: Distribution of study subjects according to Socio-demographic characteristics (n=111)

Variable	Number	Percentage (%)
Age (in years)		
≤ 19	27	24.3
≥20	84	75.7
Education		
Basic education	16	14.4
Lower secondary	54	48.7
Upper secondary	16	14.4
Post secondary	25	22.5
Socio-economic status		
Upper middle	44	39.6
Lower middle	45	40.5
Upper lower	22	19.8

Majority were primigravida (76.5%) and had a normal BMI (73.9%). Anaemia and proteinuria were detected in 44.1% and 12.6% of mothers respectively. Optimal vitamin D levels were found in only 55.9% of mothers [Table-2].

Table 2: Distribution of study population according to obstetric history, clinical examination (n=111)

Variable	Number	Percentage (%)
Gravida		
Primigravida	85	76.5
Second gravid	20	18.1
Third gravida	06	5.4
BMI		
Normal	82	73.9
Overweight	25	22.5
Obese-I	04	3.6
Anemia		
Present	49	44.1
Absent	62	55.9
Proteinuria		
Present	14	12.6
Absent	97	87.4
Vitamin D levels		
Optimal	62	55.9
Suboptimal	49	44.1

Only 15.3% of mothers had pre-eclampsia [Fig-1] and 6.3% had eclampsia [Fig-2].

Figure 1: Pre-eclampsia among study subjects (n=111)

Figure 2: Eclampsia among study subjects (n=111)

Most of them had term deliveries (74.8%) and delivered vaginally (84.7%). Nearly three-fourths (74.8%) of the babies had a birth weight over 2.5 kg and 88.3% had an APGAR score of ≥ 7 . Only 10.8% of the babies required SNCU admission [Table-3].

Table 3: Distribution of study subjects according to maternal and perinatal outcome (n=111)

Variable	Number	Percentage (%)
Gestation age		
Term	83	74.8
Preterm	28	25.2
Mode of delivery		
Vaginal	94	84.7
C-section	17	16.3
Birth weight		
<2500g	28	25.2
$\geq 2500g$	83	74.8
APGAR score		
<7	13	11.7
≥ 7	98	88.3
SNCU admission		
Yes	12	10.8
No	99	89.2

Pre-eclampsia was notably higher among mothers under 20 years old (25.9%) compared to those 20 years or older (10.7%) and was also higher among primigravida (17.6%). Pre-eclampsia was significantly higher among over weight and obese mothers compared to mothers with normal BMI ($p=0.012$). Anaemia was significantly associated with pre-eclampsia ($p=0.001$), as was proteinuria ($p=0.000$). Vaginal delivery occurred in 9.6% of pre-eclamptic cases compared to 47.1% via caesarean section which is statistically significant

($p=0.00$). Low birth weight was seen in 25% of infants born to pre-eclamptic mothers compared to 10.8% with normal birth weight. SNCU admission was required for 41.7% of infants born to pre-eclamptic mothers compared to 12.1% who did not require admission ($p=0.007$). About 8.1% of mothers with an optimal vitamin D level had pre-eclampsia, compared to those with suboptimal levels (24.5%) and it is statistically significant ($p=0.017$) [Table-4].

Table 4: Correlates of pre-eclampsia among study subjects (n=111)

Variable	Pre-eclampsia No (%)	Normal No (%)	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age (in years)				
<20	07(25.9)	20(74.1)	2.59 (0.87-7.66)	0.078
≥20	10(11.9)	74(88.1)	Ref	
Gravida				
Primigravida	15 (17.6)	70 (82.4)	1.07 (0.11-9.84)	0.367
Second gravid	01 (5.0)	19 (95.0)	0.26 (0.01-4.98)	
Third gravid	01 (16.7)	05 (83.3)	Ref	
BMI				
Overweight	07(28.0)	18(72.0)	3.59 (1.15-11.22)	0.012
Obese-I	02(50.0)	02(50.0)	9.25 (1.14-74.88)	
Normal	08(9.8)	74(90.2)	Ref	
Anemia				
Present	14(28.6)	35(71.4)	7.86(2.11-29.30)	0.001
Absent	03(4.8)	59(95.2)	Ref	
Proteinuria				
Present	09(92.8)	05(17.0)	20.02 (5.39-74.28)	0.000
Absent	08(30.0)	89(70.0)	Ref	
Mode of delivery				
C-section	08(47.1)	09(52.9)	8.39 (2.59-27.16)	0.000
Vaginal	09(9.6)	85(90.4)	Ref	
SNCU admission				
Yes	05(41.7)	07(58.3)	5.17 (1.41-18.93)	0.007
No	12(12.1)	87(87.9)	Ref	
Vitamin D levels during admission				
Suboptimal	12(24.5)	37(75.5)	3.69 (1.20-11.35)	0.017
Optimal	05(8.1)	57(91.9)	Ref	

Discussion

The present study highlighted that only 15.3% of mothers had pre-eclampsia and 6.3% had eclampsia. Pre-eclampsia was significantly higher among mothers with suboptimal levels of vitamin D (24.5%). Moreover, factors like obesity, presence of anaemia, proteinuria, vaginal delivery and admission to SNCU were significantly associated. Pre-eclampsia was higher among mothers under 20 years of age (25.9%) and primigravida (17.6%). In contrast, Bodnar et al. [10] identified preeclampsia to be higher in the age group 20-29 years but also found primigravidas as most affected. Conversely, Dahma et al. [11] and Bakacak et al. [6] reported that second gravidas were more affected, differing from our findings. Regarding risk factors, our study found higher rates of pre-eclampsia among mothers with higher BMI and suboptimal vitamin D levels (24.5%), compared to those with optimal levels (8.1%). Anaemia on admission (28.6%) and significant proteinuria (92.8%) were linked to pre-eclampsia. Additionally, our findings supported previous research linking overweight status, low vitamin D levels, and heightened pre-eclampsia risk, as observed by Bakacak et al. [6] and Naghshineh et al [13]. Pena et al. [12] found that 12.6% of mothers with pre-eclampsia had anaemia compared to only 0.6% in the non-pre-eclampsia group.

In our study, among those with pre-eclampsia, 9.6% delivered vaginally and 47.1% via caesarean section. Furthermore, 25% of infants born to pre-eclamptic mothers had low birth weight, and 41.7% required SNCU admission. Contrasting findings from other studies include Bakacak et al. [6], who noted predominantly caesarean deliveries among pre-eclamptic participants, and Dahma et al. [11], who reported higher caesarean rates among mothers receiving supplementation, unlike our findings. Pena et al. [12] reported normal birth weights among infants born to mothers with pre-eclampsia, differing from our study, while Dahma et al. [11] observed lower NICU admissions among mothers receiving Vitamin D supplementation, contrasting with our results.

Conclusion & Recommendation

Our findings indicate a close link between suboptimal vitamin D levels and pre-eclampsia and highlights significant association of other factors with it.

However, further research is needed to establish standardized guidelines for serum Vitamin D levels, optimal supplementation doses, and cost-effective testing to improve maternal and fetal health outcomes.

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